

SUSTAINABLE EXPLORATION OF THE MOON ENABLED BY A ZERO-WASTE RESOURCE UTILISATION APPROACH M. Anand¹, S. Lim¹, R.J. Windmill¹, I. J. Corfe², E. M. Jolis², S. Lukkari² and A.R.Butcher²; ¹The Open University, Walton Hall, Milton Keynes, MK7 6AA, UK, maresh.anand@open.ac.uk; ²Geological Survey of Finland, Espoo, Finland, alan.butcher@gtk.fi;

Introduction: The emerging era of lunar exploration aims to develop a more sustainable approach, which would require careful planning, preparation, and execution of surface operations, utilising the available resources on-site efficiently while minimising the impact on the local lunar environment [1]. To realise this vision, significant technological developments are taking place for lunar *in situ* resource utilisation (ISRU) [2], mainly utilising terrestrial analogues. However, the aspects of lunar ISRU research could be of immediate relevance to terrestrial applications, such as in the mining sector, which faces many similar challenges. Thus, a synergistic approach involving lunar ISRU research with potential terrestrial applications could make critical contributions to areas such as raw materials and circular economy.

Context: Several missions are in progress or being planned to enable the surface exploration of the Moon through human-robotic partnerships. These lunar surface operations are likely to involve extended stays for astronauts, including at locations that have never been visited by humans before (e.g., polar regions of the Moon or the far side). Regardless of the landing location, the most readily available resource at the Moon is the regolith, which could provide a feedstock for the extraction of critical elements such as hydrogen, oxygen, and other metals, besides being beneficial for construction processes such as 3D printed habitats, tools, and other structures [3,4]. Techniques are being developed to handle, process, and utilise the entirety of lunar regolith so that it produces zero waste. A comparable need exists on Earth in the mining sector where traditionally, a large amount of ‘waste’ is produced in extracting the target element(s), leaving a large ‘footprint’ that is often environmentally damaging and sometimes poses a danger to local communities. Thus, there is a tremendous potential for applying some of the techniques developed for lunar ISRU to the remediation of historic mine ‘waste’, and integration into current and future mining operations to improve the efficiency of mining itself while enabling cross-fertilisation of ideas between practitioners in the space sector and terrestrial mining and manufacturing industries.

A new approach: Inspired by our lunar ISRU work, we have recently embarked on a project which involved a survey of legacy mine sites in north Wales, UK, which has witnessed centuries of mining activity for metals such as Cu and Zn, along with roofing material such as slates. We conducted fieldwork to collect samples of mine ‘waste’ from four historical mine

sites (Parys Mountain, Nantlle Valley, Pandora Mine and Sygun Mine).

Figure 1. Parys Mountain historic mine site, north Wales, UK

We conducted microwave heating experiments on these samples and found that sulphides, which were previously dispersed in the ‘waste’ became concentrated into micro-nuggets, thus revealing the potential for beneficiation of metals. Subsequently, we successfully used the raw ‘waste’ as well as microwaved melted and sintered samples for 3D printing of blocks using a plant-based polymer binder (derived from food waste) as an example of how these materials could be used in construction.

Figure 2. Interlocking building bricks featuring an 8 peg-design, with studs and tubes, that are mechanically compatible with each other. It was made using a mixture of mine waste from North Wales and a plant-based polymer as the binder.

This approach allowed us to demonstrate the full utilisation of the starting material without creating any secondary waste.

Highlights: We have demonstrated the synergy between lunar ISRU and terrestrial applications that could be of significant economic value on Earth and in space. Our initial microwave experiments on mine ‘waste’ are highly encouraging for the beneficiation of metallic elements, some of which were not targeted in the original mining operations (e.g., only Cu was targeted in a rock where other elements such as Zn and Pb or even Ni and Co might have also been present). Furthermore, by successfully printing 3D structures using raw and microwave-treated mine ‘waste’, we ensured zero waste of the original feedstock. All these attributes would be even more significant for lunar applications. We are also planning to add a processing stage to extract oxygen from the regolith, alongside metals, before utilising the remaining material for 3D printing purposes.

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References: [1] Anand et al. (2012) *Planet. Space Sci.*, 74(1); [2] Spedding et al. (2021) *Acta Astronaut.*, 181; [3] Lim et al., (2021) *Sci. Rep.*, 11(1); [4] Lim et al., (2023) *Sci. Rep.*, 13(1).